

Research Article

The Traditional Chinese Medicine and Holographic System of human Body

Cao Jun¹ and Feng Qing^{2*}

¹Yatai Yongan Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., China

²Beijing Wantongyi Biological Science and Technology Co., Ltd., China

Section I

An Overview of Hologram

The 3-D version of the movie “Avatar” initiated people’s concern with the importance of the hologram. Hologram is three dimensional. People’s comprehension of hologram comes from holography. Based on the theory of optical interference, scientists applied the diffraction of laser on photography, thus a three-dimensional photo was produced. Even if the photo was torn apart, laser could put all pieces together and restore fully the original photo.

The concept of organ manifestation in the Chinese Medicine is also a holographic expression. This concept stresses that a person’s exterior can indicate the conditions of the organs inside the body. The Chinese Medicine firmly believes that “any interior problems would have indications on the exterior.” All interior organs have indications on the exterior. A local point contains holographic information. To interpret “organ manifestation” into modern language, it could be rendered as the “holographic information of organs.”

As a matter of fact, the Chinese Medicine does not have to rely on health check-ups or tests when it comes to judge if a person is healthy. By observing the appearance of the patient, by auscultation and olfaction, by interrogation and pulse-feeling, a doctor of the Chinese Medicine would find out the physical conditions of the patient. This can really work wonders and this is what we call the “correlation of the four examinations,” which is the process of collecting and receiving the holographic information of the organs. The diagnose by the Chinese Medicine doctors looks very much like fortune tellers. The only difference is that the doctors only talk about health, not about fortune.

We can therefore say without any exaggeration that the holistic view of the Chinese Medicine is naturally a holographic view and

*Corresponding author: Feng Qing, Beijing Wantongyi Biological Science and Technology Co., Ltd., China, Tel: +86 13051327979; E-mail: feng-qing@vip.sina.com

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the earliest of it. The word for manifestation in organ, pulse and sky manifestations and the word for looks in facial looks share the same pronunciation in the Chinese language; even though they are written differently, they all contain the meaning of holographic information.

We used to say “your face reveals what is in your mind.” Eyes often speak your mind. Facial looks often express one’s emotions. Normally a person’s face would have a change at around forty years of age, and such a change would record your good or evil deeds, your sorrows and happiness and your behaviors in the first half of your life. Your childhood playmates wouldn’t be able to recognize you at the first glance. After this change there would not be any major changes on your face in the rest of your life. Generally speaking, a Buddha like person would have a benign countenance; a thief like person would have a sneaky look; a criminal would have a malicious look and a patient would look listless.

Bio-Holographic Theory

Bio-holographic theory is a hypothesis, which supposes that a part carries the entire information of the wholeness. The chief motivator at the present time of this theory is Professor Zhang Yingching of Shandong University of China.

Professor Zhang Yingching put forward the concept of “the law of bio-hologram” in 1973. By observing the law of layout of a group of points on the side of the second metacarpal bone, which resembles the human body in reduced scale, and by observing the emerging of two earthworms from two separate cut parts of one earthworm, he proposed a hypothesis in 1985 about “bio-holographic embryo and holographic element” [1].

Professor Zhang Yingching’s hypothesis was verified in 1996 when the British successfully cloned the famous world’s first sheep “Dolly” by using totipotent stem cell. Professor Zhang has been regarded as the first person in the world in the study of bio-hologram. The Science and Technology section in the Chinese Embassy in Sweden held that Professor Zhang, as a Chinese, was the closest to winning a Nobel Prize in Biology and Medicine.

Unfortunately, in between 1995 and 1996, a few so called “fighters against falsehood”, putting on high morality cloaks, branded Professor Zhang’s theory as “false science”. This is just like putting a square peg into a round hole, and as a result, Professor Zhang’s theory was forced out in the academic circle, and Professor Zhang’s article to refute and defend himself was not allowed to be published. Much to our regret Professor Zhang passed away in 2004 without being cleared from wrong criticisms. Up to now, the science circle in China is still indignant and sorrowful about this painful lesson.

It seems that the East and the West, and the Chinese Medicine and the Western Medicine do agree, without any mutual discussions, on the existence of hologram about human body despite of some minor discrepancies. Hologram is not at all the “patent” of the Chinese Medicine, even though it started to use the theory in its diagnoses by

instinct several thousand years ago. Modern Medicine's explanation of the holographic theory is more scientific and convincing than that of the Chinese Medicine.

Human-Hologram

Biology is a large category, which includes both plants and animals; man is among animals, since man is the senior type of all animals. If the bio-holographic theory can be radicated, the study of human-hologram can then be started. Such studies would contribute much more to the study of life science. Practical as human-hologram is, it is still a discipline to be completed. Even though, people take it for granted as one plus one is two in its application in manual skills or natural therapies such as massage, pedicure and hand treatment, human-hologram is still a hypothesis to be continuously verified.

The Evolution of Human-Hologram

There is a process for the evolution of human-hologram. If we took man's cell as a holographic element, the four limbs and five organs on the face are naturally holographic embryos. Embryos, bigger than the element, leave much room for people's imagination to develop human-hologram.

The human being is good at drawing analogies among things. Enlightened by the macrocosm and microcosm, and taking reference of the motion of the planet in the solar system, the British physical scientist Ernest Rutherford proposed one hypothesis, which was later confirmed with scientific methods by scientist Niels Bohr as the theory of atomic model [2].

Some people, both Chinese and foreigner, discovered later that the contour of an ear of man resembles very much to a curled-up baby. They then boldly supposed that this "baby's" head and facial features may have some homologous relationship with those of a man.

They also noticed that the outer flank of a person's foot resembles very much like the cervical spine, the thoracic, lumbar and sacral vertebrae of a sitting person, they then presumed that there must be some homologous relationship with a man's five deposit and six transit organs.

As a Chinese saying goes: when one fully grasps a matter, he would find it easier to understand things similar. So, these people presumed that a person's hand would be the same, that is to say some kind of holographic reflection area can be found on the hand, which correspond with interior organs of the body.

Imagination creates talent. The bold hypothesis such as the embryonic form of hologram, the probe into corresponding parts with interior organs constitute the rudimentary form of human holographic theory.

In 1917, Mr. Fitzgerald, a British Ear, Nose and Throat doctor put forward the theory of reflection and a chart of human reflection zones, and on basis of this theory, he created reflexology. He published in 1917 "Zone Therapy", in which he gave charts of human reflection zones, and he divided the body into ten vertical zones, and each serve as a miniature of body information.

Up to now, the Europeans are still using "The Vega Iris Zone Chart", which is a holographic diagram of iris summarized by Leon Vanier, who observed a hundred thousand pairs of eyes and extracted from each side of the eye a hundred and sixty reflection zones, which

correspond to one side of the body and organ tissues on that side. Besides the above, the German Acupuncture Journal carried a diagram drawn by a French Surgeon Dr. P. Nogier, which is entitled: "Layout of Points on the Ear in the Shape of an Upside Down Embryo."

There have been many more efforts in the same direction. Views and theories, based on China's traditional foot massage, ranging from holographic embryo to human reflection zones developed by people in Europe and Americas such as the UK, the USA, Germany, Switzerland, Sweden and Austria. Everyone involved is trying to make head ways by every possible means to strive in the field of hologram for a success, similar to that made by C. Columbus when he made an egg stand on its own. They hope a theory could be thus created and a big prize might be forthcoming in the world for them.

Zheng Mingde, a Chinese Medicine expert held that any pathological change with interior organs would be reflected on corresponding points in the ear, hand and foot, for the ear, hand and foot are epitomes of man and contain entire biological and genetic information of man.

The Definition of Human-Hologram

The definition of the human-hologram can be expressed as: the human body is holographic and contains holographic elements and holographic embryos. The holographic elements have different series. The earlier the series the better the holographic element. Holographic elements constitute a holographic embryo. The chemical constituent of DNA of every independent part on the human body, no matter of holographic element or holographic embryo, is the same as the entire body and is an epitome of the whole.

Every cell of man is a holographic element. The 32 cell split from the fertilized egg are totipotent stem cells, which are of the highest series and most complete in holographic information, and can be used in a clone of the entire body of a human being. The next series is the multipotent stem cell, which could be split into various organs of a human being. The next series is pluripotent stem cell, which could be split into blood cells and lymph cells. The lowest series is the unipotent stem cell, which could only be split into a single cell tissue.

The limbs and body of a person are holographic embryos that can be used for recuperating and curing purposes. In the holographic embryo, there are reflection zones corresponding to the five deposit organs and the six transit organs, by stimulating these zones, the interior organs can be regulated and the functional obstacles can be removed.

Cytology Is a Prove of Hologram in the Human Body

The material basis of human-hologram is cytology. The Western Medicine holds that the human body is composed of organs, organs are composed of tissues and tissues are composed of cells or cell mass, and cell is composed of protein and ribonucleic acid in the form of DNA. The ribonucleic acid is what the bio-chemists think the smallest material inside human body. In principle, everyone's DNA is exclusive, and his DNA in each cell is the same. We therefore say DNA is the body's finger print, which could be used as statutory evidence. What should be stressed here is that DNA is holographic, so every cell is certainly holographic as well.

Human-hologram holds that a holographic element refers to a structural unit that has a specific form and basic function, which can reflect information of the entire body, and has a relatively distinct border to other parts around it. If a holographic element was similar to

a cell, then the holographic embryo would be similar to embryos and organs. If we could prove cells in the human body are holographic, then tissues, organs and limbs or embryos that are composed of cells are also holographic. Such is the inductive logic of human-hologram.

The results of the global “Human Genome Project” launched off in 1990 show that cells are holographic. DNA in human cells is just like a handset cord, which has a double helix. If you pull at the double helix, it would then become a helix staircase, and the stairs are made of purine and pyrimidine in sea food and beef soup, which are to be connected in fixed AT, CG patterns. If the connection was not done in fixed patterns, a cancer cell would be produced. Among thousands of stairs, some recorded the genetic code, some didn't. We then call the stairs that recorded the information as “genes”. Every DNA has thirty to forty thousand genes. A gene would record all physical features of a person, such like the height, skin color, hair, eyes and etc. It also records the genetic code of history of family diseases. We therefore say DNA in cells is holographic.

In theory, if a person's nucleated cell can be obtained, then all of his genes could be collected on the DNA stairs. With these genes, all his physical features, that is to say all his human-holographic information can be outlined by a computer.

Cell differentiation is not the same as cell split. With the former, the DNA would continuously split and reproduce itself along a designated direction until one organ, for instance, an eye, a liver or a hand is finally formed.

To further our understanding of cell differentiation and cell split, we wish to cite the following example. In the actual process of creating man, a fertilized egg is a genetic cell that carries half of its father's hologram and half of its mother's hologram. After the fertilized egg is implanted, its cell begins to split into two, and then the split would be repeated once. By then, in the tiny fertilized egg there are four tiny cells and each of them would be split into two. So far, there has only been splitting, no differentiation as yet. In normal circumstance, among the first bunch of splitting, the 32 cells are all totipotent stem cells. If each of the 32 totipotent stem cells is extracted and placed into the womb of 32 mothers, there would then be 32 persons of the same height, same blood type, same features, and they would be the same in every respect.

As the totipotent stem cell is of the highest series, it can reproduce man by itself. Multipotent stem cell ranks next in the series; it can reproduce organs of man. Pluripotent stem cell ranks the third in the series; it can reproduce blood cell and lymph cell. Unipotent stem cell is of the lowest in the series, it can only reproduce itself. If a unipotent stem cell is differentiated, it could become pluripotent stem cell; if a pluripotent stem cell is differentiated, it could become multipotent stem cell, which could be used to clone sheep and other living beings and it could also clone a heart or other organs that have not gone through the rejection phase. Pluripotent stem cell can be used to treat leucocythemia. The unipotent stem cell can be used without treatment to clone bruised organ cells, skin cells and endometrial cells. After a body is being born, there are a great amount of unipotent stem cells and aging pluripotent stem cells in it. These are all in the scope of studies by the great stem cell engineering.

It should be stressed that the DNA in each of the above cells is the same. DNA is a secretive, invisible chief commander to give unified command to the splitting and reproduction of all cells. When one cell

is deceased a new one would be reproduced. The ones that do not listen to the command are cancer cells, which run amuck and piled up as a disease of cancer. DNA gives its command by “order”, which should be a bio wave. A bio wave is holographic; therefore, it is able to command the cells in organs to conduct splitting and reproduction according to demand.

Human cytology reveals the material basis of human-hologram. We should give this credit to the molecular biology in the Western Medicine, not to the theory of organ-graph in the Chinese Medicine.

It Is the Statistics That Rendered Human-Hologram into Science

Back in the 20th century, some Westerners, before they made it clear of what the energy of Qi and the information of waves were and why the two of them could be used in treating diseases, scooped others in putting forward the idea of holographic therapy. They firmly believed that hologram could assist the curing of diseases, they found on the limbs and facial organs reflection zones to interior organs by way of using analogy and the reflection of pain. These people resorted to the statistics, which was created by Westerners, in their deduction of a “statistical conclusion” through “hypothesis testing”, and thus packaged holographic therapy with the cloak of science.

It has been known to everybody that statistics is the midwife of science. After going through the rigorous process of “hypothesis testing” and removing some “small probability events”, some chemical laboratory experiments and studies of the human body, which were not really necessarily to be regarded as science at the beginning, were given a “birth certificate” of science and become a full-fledged science. And this was how the holographic medicine was born.

We should recognize that in this period holographic medicine had made great progress in the West, and some holographic medicine theories on the eye, ear, hand and foot took shape and were independent to each other, and thus made indelible contributions to studies of the mankind itself. In despite of the fact that these unfettered Westerners who made some breakthrough in holographic medicine and who have been more advanced than the Chinese in the practice of holographic reflection therapy, their theory and practice have not yet been affirmed by the mainstream of the Western Medicine, and they are still walking back and forth outside the gate of this mainstream. This is really a pity.

Section II

Human Hologram Reflection

A new leap in theory was attained by the Chinese after they blended the Western holographic medicine with the traditional Chinese Medicine by way of “bringing exported goods for domestic marketing” at the end of the last century. In practice, hologram has acquired actual treatment significance after the Chinese Medicine applied the manual skills of massage, acupuncture and breath-exercise onto the holographic chart of the eye, ear and foot. Such a perfect blending delivered human-hologram back into the hands of the Chinese Medicine. For instance, the ear hologram has evolved into acupuncture points and reflection zone treatment in the ear, which has been included in the textbooks of acupuncture in the Chinese Medicine. The manual skills in the Chinese Medicine are divided into skills on points along the meridian and skills of reflection zones.

Most massage therapists in the Chinese Medicine are not able to give a clear account of what human-hologram is, yet, every one of

them is a good speaker when giving a discourse of holographic reflection zones.

The Hologram Reflection Is Hologram Plus Reflection

What is of practical significance to ordinary people is not the verification of the theory of human-hologram, but its actual application. We thus conceived the wording of Human Hologram Reflection. By adding the word “reflection”, hologram is no longer a status, but a process of commuting holographic information. Human-hologram has static elements and embryos. Human hologram reflection has dynamic hologram net and hologram field. (This will be further explored in Section III—“Man Has a Third Life System—Holographic System”.)

In the society, there are people who use holographic reflection in fortune telling and people who use it to treat diseases. On the streets, signage of foot reflection therapy is easy to find. In bookstores, it is not difficult to single out a book about reflection zones. The fact that in the above instances what is “reflection” has not been fully explained reveals a deliberate blurring of nervous reflection and holographic reflection. We could detest from such a behavior the potential demand of reflection treatment in the market and at the same time the longing of a clear discourse of reflection.

As a matter of fact, being the direction of holographic medicine, human hologram reflection is composed of both human-hologram and holographic reflection. We have given a brief introduction to human-hologram in the foregoing; we shall now conduct an initial quest of main components of human hologram reflection, so that our successors could somehow be prompted when they try to improve this theory.

Reflection Is a Holographic Transmission of Signals

Being static, human-hologram is the category of studies of biochemistry, molecular biology and cytology; yet the human hologram reflection is dynamic and falls in the category of studies of biophysics, molecular physics and bioelectromagnetic.

Human hologram reflection refers to the effect on the corresponding organs to the reflection zones of holographic elements and embryos after a stimulus has been triggered onto them and vice versa, because reflection is bidirectional. What transmits the stimulus is the bioelectromagnetic wave.

The bidirectional signal transmission of hologram reflection includes downward reception and return transmission. The downward reception refers to the response or reflections on local parts of the body such as the eye, face, hand and sole of foot of malign signals about the interior organs, which appear as abnormal skin color, texture and bumps and are often accompanied with pain. This is very similar to the observation among the four examinations in the Chinese Medicine.

The Downward Reception of Reflection—Diagnose

The downward signals, in particular signals of pain, of reflection serves as the basis of diagnose. Pain is a warning signal endowed to mankind by the God for the need to go to a doctor. Pain is a process, it might be obtuse when it starts and acute when it develops. The patient might be totally freed if the pain becomes unbearable. Pain, however, is holographic, and it has been classified into different categories, and an independent theory has been formed about it. This is none the

less in the scope of studies by the Western Medicine. Yet, what the Western Medicine probes into are local parts of the body without any consideration of references to the organ diseases.

It can hardly be a comprehensive judgment if only the four examinations were used in collection of hologram when it comes to diagnose organ diseases. During observation, when the doctor looks at the facial expressions of the patient, it is difficult to know whether the suffering of the patient is physical reflection or a psychological reflection, or whether it is conditioned reflex or a neural reflex. But, the pain reflection does not cheat you. If the doctor touched on the where it hurt, the patient would naturally give you an unbearable expression.

The feature of the holographic reflex is that the hurting points on limbs and facial organs do correspond to the problem in the interior organ in question. These hurting points are the reflection zone of this organ. If you put together all reflection zones accurately, you would then have an independent chart of human hologram reflection.

Up to now, the discovery of reflection zones is still hypothesis set forth by people in the periphery of both the Chinese and Western Medicine, who have tried to probe into laws of pain on thousands and millions of people. A final conclusion cannot be drawn because such a hypothesis is still to be supported by any chemical tests and its concomitant physical measurement.

The Upward Transmission—Treatment

If the downward reception of holographic reflection was for diagnose, then, the upward transmission of holographic reflection is for treatment. The upward return transmission of the signals of holographic reflection refers to the process that stimulus signals, produced by massage or acupuncture on the reflection zones of limbs after the doctor has given his diagnose, have reached the remote five deposit organs and the six transmit organs for purpose of curing.

Massage and acupuncture in the Chinese Medicine are the earliest in using holographic reflection of pain for curing purposes, which have a history of over several thousand years. By relying on the meridian chart left over by their ancestors, the doctors of the Chinese Medicine are deeply convinced of the effectiveness of curing by Qi. The manual skills in the Chinese Medicine are a typical “treatment of pain”. Most hurting points, which are not caused by wound, reflect problems with organs, not muscles. It really works wonders when massage and acupuncture are done on hurting points. The traditional Chinese Medicine calls those hurting spots that are not the points along the meridians “living acupuncture points”.

Living acupuncture points are holographic reflection points on the limbs corresponding to organs. If the heart had a problem, the reflection points on the limbs would be very painful. Yet, few can give a positive answer to the following questions: should these hurting points be dealt with by the holographic reflection zone in the Western Medicine or by the living acupuncture points in the theory of the meridian of the Chinese Medicine? And at the same time, do the relative manual skills belong to the holographic reflection treatment or to the acupuncture treatment in the meridian theory?

Backed up by the meridian chart as a theory, doctors of acupuncture do not mind much of the connotation of holographic reflection. There must be some common effect of treatment in both meridian and holographic reflection even in acupuncture. However, the doctors of massage, and in particular massage on foot and hand, do mind much

of human holographic reflection, because there are often not circulating meridians or points corresponding to where they massage on.

Reflexology and Natural Therapy

Reflexology is a new therapy that blends manual skills and breathing exercise of the Chinese Medicine with reference to hologram and the theory of the meridians.

Ever since the 19th century, there has been a health preserving method, which is being used to regulate the five deposit organs and the six transmit organs by manual skills and breathing exercise without taking of any drugs, and if there is anything to be taken, they are natural material. Such a method is called Natural Therapy. With the spring up of acupuncture and massage clinics of the Chinese Medicine all over the globe, this method has become a fashion for both Chinese and foreign personages pursuing longevity.

The effect of the natural therapy is both holographic and meridian. What this method marshalls are Qi and the bioelectromagnetic wave diffracted from Qi, which are used to cure pains and regulate organs by the spreading of Qi and the transmission of bio-waves of Qi. As far as the energy of Qi, the transmission and exchange of information are concerned, they should be studied by the Chinese Medicine and the Information Medicine in a joint effort.

The combination of reflexology and the meridian therapy of the Chinese Medicine belong to a typical natural therapy. Its manuduction skills include: manipulation, massage, acupuncture, cupping, scraping and bloodletting puncture and etc. Its breathing exercise therapy includes: maneuvering of Qi, pressing of points, sitting in meditation and Taiji boxing and etc. Aside from the Chinese Medicine, other therapies applied include: nutrition, aromatic, detoxification, physical, psychological, music, environment, home therapy, SPA, yoga, meditation and etc.

Section III

The Third Set of Life System of Man—the Holographic System

It is known to all that according to the theory of the Western Medicine there is an anatomical system in the body of man; according to the theory of the Chinese Medicine, there is a meridian system in the body of man. Both systems can cure diseases. However, there seems to be a set of human hologram system outside the two systems.

Why Does the Hologram System Exist?

The theory of the meridians in the Chinese Medicine is good enough to explain the effects of acupuncture and manuduction. Yet, that theory is not good enough to explain massage and acupuncture on the ear, and massage on the hand and foot, neither could it explain how the interior organs could be improved from a remote end. Because there are no points on the ear, and there are only a few points on the hand, and there is only one point, the Yongquan point on the foot that connects with the Qi from the earth, and there is almost no running of the meridians on the foot. There is truly no warrant in the theory of the meridians to manuduction on the foot.

People then tried to find out if there was anything similar to the neural reflex in the anatomical system. Much to their disappointment, the peripheral nerves on the foot could only transmit neural signals of warmth, coldness and pain, and they are not really related to such autonomic nerves that govern the interior organs. It is a bit too far-fetched to explain foot manuduction with neural reflex.

What theory that can really back up foot manuduction is the obscured blending of human hologram reflex and the theory of the meridians. If the practice of massage on the ear, the hand and the sole of foot could lead to the discovery of some laws of human hologram reflex, and the existence of the corresponding relations between the human holographic zones and interior organs, then there must be the existence of a third life system—the human hologram system aside from the connections of the anatomical and the meridian systems. Such would be an entirely new “century discovery”, worth of attention of a Nobel Prize. Our knowledge of the human body would be more complete if we use the theory of anatomy, the meridian and the hologram in our observations.

The Holographic Net and the Holographic Field

It still remains a mystery of what connects the reflection zones with organs. It is not convincing to say the connection is done by nerve, the meridian or the chemical matter from endocrine; they are not the passage or the media for the transmission of wireless signals.

The adoption of the concepts of holographic net and holographic field is crucial to the fate of human hologram reflex. The exchange of signals is only possible when there is a field, which could activate holographic signals. Otherwise, human holographic signals will remain as static elements and embryos; their only good is to serve as subjects to be studied by scientists.

The Holographic Net

Conversations on mobile phones, the exchange in “We Talk” on the information platform on intelligent on cell phones rely on the mobile internet, which is a physical net and its signals can be gauged. The exchange of human hologram relies on a biological net of the human body itself. What it transmits is very weak bio-wave, which could not be detested even by the most updated technique of today.

The holographic medicine resembles very much to the Chinese Medicine, for which there are theories and laws; yet, the subject matter to be studied does not seem to be visible. At least, it is not visible to man’s visual sense. In virtue of ultra-microscope, we are able to see actual and various cells in anatomy, such as a nerve cell or a neuron, but never a holographic element or embryo and either a holographic net.

The meaning of “holographic element” might have taken from the word “neuron”, which sends messages to and from brain; the word “element” in “holographic element” also serves as a base to send and receive signals. Mr. Zhang Yingqing, the inventor argued that the holographic element is the material base for the entire bio-hologram and the foundation of the theory of bio-hologram. As it has been revealed in cytology that the DNA in human cells are holographic, therefore the cells themselves are holographic as well, and further, organs and limbs that are composed of cells are also holographic. The hypothesis of the holographic element and embryo was finally verified as true after contention that cells are holographic and limbs are partially holographic embryos proved to be right.

Just as the holographic element, the holographic net is an objective existence. It is very much like the Qi and the meridian; nobody can prove that they do not exist despite of their invisibility. We wish to borrow a famous saying from Einstein here: we shall never be able to prove things that do not exist.

There are many things that do exist yet invisible. The mobile internet for cell phones is invisible, yet it is handy at all times to transmit messages for us. The internet is connected to a designated number. Man's five deposit organs and six transit organs also have designated numbers, and perhaps their end numbers are connected to numerous cells and cell mass on the limbs. To borrow a word from the human hologram glossary, the holographic end numbers of organs are connected with numerous holographic elements and embryos on the limbs. That's why when there is a problem with one organ, the person in question would not feel well all over his body.

It is the holographic net that makes the exchange of human hologram possible. The holographic net is, however, unidirectional; it only works on its own system and has no effect on other systems. For instance, if we massage on the reflection zones of the kidney on the ear or the sole of foot, the kidney and the reflection zones to kidney on the hand, the head and other places on the body will feel tightened or relaxed, and at the same time, other organs will not be affected. This resembles a lot to the handling of traffic jams in the Chinese cities. Every day there are cars with a certain groups of numbers on their license plates are not allowed on the streets. Such a ban is unidirectional. On a given day, only cars with a set group of end numbers are not allowed on the roads, no matter the size of vehicles, and at the same time, cars with other end numbers on their plates are allowed on the road. When an organ runs into a problem, its reflection zones would be most sensitive to pains. Such is the special feature of human hologram reflex.

The Holographic Field

The holographic field is different from the holographic net. The human holographic field is, as a matter of fact, the field of Qi, which is divided into a haploid field and a mass or diploid field. The Qi field could be an information field or an energy field. Qi itself is energy. Energy can produce work. Energy can release bio-wave. Smell and color could be derived from the vibration of bio-wave. If we took pith, Qi and spirit emphasized in the Chinese Medicine as the incarnation of the three elements of the universe, namely material, energy and information respectively, then, the pith is material, Qi is energy and spirit is the field of Qi, and on top of it, the holographic field.

It was the religion of the Taoist who was the first to use the concept of the Qi field. Taoism argues that as long as there is life, there is Qi, and there is the masculine or the sunny Qi and the feminine or cloudy Qi. The Taoist school attaches importance to the practice of breathing exercise. The Taoist medicine is the precedent of the Chinese Medicine. Almost all well-known doctors of the Chinese Medicine, for instance, Bian Que, Hua Tuo, Zhang Zhongjing, Sun Simiao, Ge Hong and Tao Hongjing were all Taoist doctors. As for the present, the main stream of the contingent of the Chinese Medicine is Confucian doctors, and even there is talking about Qi in their theoretic basis of these Confucian doctors, there isn't anything about breathing exercise or the Qi field. In the recent one hundred years, the theory of the Qi field has been fashionable in Europe and America, where people put on a cloak of science on the Qi field in their books and included it into the courseware of psychology and communications. However, their Qi field has nothing to do with the holographic field. Their Qi field talks about creating a certain kind of atmosphere, a kind of technique of presentation for politicians and marketing persons, so that they could seem to be appealing, affectionate or aggressive to their audience.

The concept of holographic field is most efficient in the explanation of the outcome of manual skills in the Chinese Medicine. In the course of manuduction, both the doctor and the patient are being enclosed by the invisible holographic field, which is playing a key role in the treatment. Someone compared the effect of acupuncture on the points to electric current that is produced by the line of magnetic force when cutting metal in the study of physics, for they held that the movement of needles caused some change of the magnetic field in a spot. As a matter of fact, the movement of needles can also cause a holistic change in the human holographic field.

Even though there is no movement of metal, no cutting by the line of magnetic force in the manuduction, there is the effect of a field all the same. This must be the holographic field. Manuduction is an all-round stimulation. When the doctor is stimulating the reflection zone of the kidney, aside from the holographic reflex in the kidney and related organs, there will also be a domino effect in the immune system, the endocrine system and the nerve system, and further improve the total balance of the human holographic field.

It is more convincing to explaining the results of acupuncture and manual skills of the Chinese Medicine with the concept of the holographic field. In nature, only when there is the effect of field, a physical reaction could be quickly produced. The iron sand on a plate would be arrayed by south and north poles when a magnet is moving underneath the plate. In daily life, someone would faint when receiving a needle or at the sight of blood; the spreading of such instant responses could only be explained by the holographic field of the bio-magnetic waves and any other explanation such as the transmission of chemical media or the transmission through the nerve system is incompetent.

Interpretation of Hologram from the Perspective of Physics

The Bio-Magnetic Wave and the Field Effect: It must be emphasized that the hypothesis of the holographic net and holographic field is based on the existence of bio-magnetic wave inside human body. A Chinese scientist in Russia, Dr. Jiang Kanzheng proved in the 60s and 70s of the last century that the material attribute of the holographic field or the Qi field rests with the bio-magnetic field. As long as a person is alive, the fundamental article would be in motion endlessly, and the bio-magnetic wave would be radiating from different cells to the outside of his body.

Messages are the outcome of the effect of waves. Waves of different length and frequency represent messages from different cells and lesions. Of course, fundamental articles including an atom and articles smaller than the atom do not have entire information features. Molecules represent attributes of species, and therefore are holographic. Human bio-wave is holographic. Holographic reflex mainly uses the length and frequency of the reflex of pain.

Pain is a holographic message when the ill Qi gets together inside the body, which reflects the imbalance of several systems. The message of pain is a kind of electro-magnetic wave, which gives directions to man's instinct manuduction and pressing of the aching points along the route of pain. Sometimes, the route of pain and the aching points spread orderly on an entire meridian on the human body, and at other times, pains cannot be explained by the diseases in the anatomical system; and sometimes, pains are not on the meridians and they are only the field effect of pain. All these can only be explained when the holographic net and field has been introduced.

Field effect produces resonance. There is an intrinsic relationship between the mass, diploid and the haploid field effect. If we took haploid field effect as a racket ball, or a shooting, then the holographic field would be a squash court or a shooting range. The ball or the bullet that are being shot carries energy and goes through the media of air to the bull's eye. The results of the shooter and the competing atmosphere in the range would affect each other, and further a holistic field effect is produced. The role of the home field for the basketball or soccer is even more obvious. The passionate scoring desire of every member of the home team and the home spectators produce the strongest holographic field effect on the performance of individual team members. In medicine, the mass holographic field comes from the exchanges among hospitalized patients and the confidence of and encouragement from the doctors.

If the treatment by the haploid holographic reflex works, the positive message would produce continuous amplified field effect, and would give positive adjustment to relative organs and systems. This is the intrinsic cause for simultaneous improvement of the immune, nerve and endocrine systems when such Chinese Medicine manual skills as foot massage and hand manuduction are being applied.

The Fundamental Articles: The fundamental articles at the time of the formation of the universe have been the material base of everything in the world. Regardless of whether it is alive or lifeless or plant or animal, or the most primordial inferior animal or the mankind, it is the fundamental article that constituted their physical nature. They therefore have acquired such physical attributes as material, energy and having a field. Universe articles from celestial bodies caused on the earth some "occult" and "spiritual" occurrences, which led to various interpretations of them by different religions and drew attention from scientists of astrophysics, bio-physics and life science.

Many of those ordinary people who practice meditation could acutely feel the "injection" from the Baihui point on top of the head universal energy, which is a positive energy that is able to drive away evil intentions and evil Qi, to upgrade one's own positive energy and even sense the existence of soul. The enlightened soul would open one's heart to the universe, and would foster a special group of volunteers with good will and kindness, who love peace, protect environment, assist the weak and bring the unlimited universe positive energy into play. Love is a holographic fundamental article, which could be amplified with positive feedback or be counteracting with negative feedback.

What we are certain of is that both universe and human fundamental articles carry positive or negative electric charges. The transmission of energy among charges is done through a field. The process is completed through different channels, which might be the meridian, the nerve passage or the passages in the holographic net. We don't know much about the relations between the fundamental article and human consciousness and soul, which is not the focus of this book.

Qi Is a Fundamental Article and Has the Nature of a Wave: The Taoist school and the Chinese Medicine regard Qi as the basic element in the formation of the sky, the earth and human being. The Qi of the sky is masculine and sunny and the Qi of the earth is feminine and cloudy. They also argue that Qi has energy, that Qi and blood are the basis of life. The Chinese Medicine believes that Qi is gathered in organs, performs on skin surface and goes to the four limbs. Qi is regarded in the Chinese Medicine the "fundamental article" that constitutes life.

As far as this point is concerned, both the simple Chinese Medicine and the modern physics reached the same destination through different routes. Both of them think the material world and the human body are made of the unified fundamental article or the Qi. In the fundamental article or the Qi, there is energy, and the movement of energy exists and is active in a kind of field.

Aside from the fundamental article, which has a twin in the Chinese Medicine, the Qi field in the Chinese Medicine also has a counterpart in modern physics, which is "field". The human body has quite a number of fields, the one that has been verified is the electro-magnetic field, and the one that is to be verified is the holographic field. The verified electro-magnetic field shows to us that the radiation of man's rate of power from his electro-magnetic field is 10 milliwatts per square millimeter, as it has been so tested. The entire human body could produce 100 watts approximately. That affirms us that there is human electro-magnetic field and the electro-magnetic energy. Low frequency field, that is to say the electric resistance and electric wave in the brain and on the skin and their accompanying electric energy can be measured. The Taoist doctors in the Chinese Medicine believe the existence of Qi field even though they don't know what physics is.

A lie detector used by man is based on physical electronics and psychology and is used to test changes in such physical references as the electric wave in the brain and the myoelectricity and further to determine if what is being said is true or false. Scholars in Taiwan argue that the transmission of blood is made possible by resonance between the cells and the heart, for the cells beat with that of the heart. Scholars on the mainland of China added that the resonance of cells is not enough in its power to pump up and circulate the blood, what helps is the rhythm of peristalsis of the blood vessel walls controlled by the nerve center of the brain. Beside that, the Qi released from cells is energy and at the same time material. It has been verified by the tests in science institutions that the Qi in the Chinese Medicine has acquired the features of waves, which have frequency, amplitude, superimposition and reduction as well.

Man speaks at a frequency of 95-142Hz; woman speaks at a frequency of 272-558Hz. The Buddhist doctors in the Chinese Medicine believe that the resonance between man and the sky is of a low frequency. The frequency of the Buddhist music and its incantation is of that kind. Music therapy can release tension and improve the physical conditions of cells. This hypothesis is certainly worth of studying by scientists.

The Chinese Medicine has always believed that it is the movement of Qi that circulates the blood, as it is so rightly said, "Qi is the Marshall of blood." Both the vibration of cells and the peristalsis of blood vessels are activated by the energy of man's Qi; these movements are some kind of mechanic movements, which all produce vector field in physics.

From another perspective, in the course of human hologram reflex, the fundamental articles (i.e. Qi and blood) in the human body can not only transmit energy, which is a physical feature, it can also produce some chemical changes, and further it can change the pattern of human bio-field.

It is known to all those physical changes do not generate anything new, but chemical changes can. A human body is material, which possesses both physical and chemical attributes. Such has been verified in the traditional life science. What is to be further verified by the

mankind is the changes in physical attributes occurred in the course of the Chinese Medicine treatment and the treatment with holographic medicine. We are not saying things to be verified do not exist. We are not saying that we can feel them, that they are not useful or not effective in curing diseases.

The Perceivable Holographic Qi Field: Qi is the fundamental “article” on the human body. The hologram field is Qi field, which is composed of an information field and an energy field. They are an objective existence, have been perceived by man in different degrees. It is much easier for a man who has been doing breathing exercise to feel and sense the Qi field. Qi field of man is a hologram field of bio-magnetic wave, which delivers energy and information by bio-waves.

The Qi field of man is very straight forward and seeks likeminded. In a gathering, one who has not practiced breathing exercise can easily find out who is not his cup of tea and becomes a bit alert of that man. There isn't much reason in it, but it is something you would instantly notice. Therefore, such a Qi field might be a typical “information field”.

Man's field emanates to the outside. The bio-magnetic wave can take the form of a Buddhist halo, or a rainbow on a human body; it can also take the form of different odors. Both cases show to us the existence of Qi inside a human body and it is holographic. Such is the performance of an information field.

An information field could be used directly in treatment. There are very old methods in using the information field, for instance, in the Taoist religion, there is “stating cause of illness when giving a prayer”, during which a talisman is drawn to drive away things evil. Some meters are very up to date, the information collector produced two years ago in Europe and America can tell you all the information about your health after your name, date and place of birth are input into the device. Another gadget is a testing stick, what you should do with it is to hold it in your hand only, a few minutes later, all health check indicator numbers would appear on the computer. The two devices are all quite accurate and really work wonders. Of course, such endeavors are in the scope of “information medicine”, which has a broad prospect.

Let us take the injection of green enzyme, the tiny bit dose can affect the whole body. What works isn't the drug, but the information because in one shot of it, more than 90% is water. What the injection of green enzyme delivers is information. In theory, as long as the information of positive energy can form a field, it then could not only cure diseases, but also drive away evil Qi and things rotten.

Aside from being an information field, the hologram field is also a field of energy. Every master and practitioner of breathing exercise in the morning parks in China can verify the existence of haploid Qi field or a mass Qi field. Energy would be produced in the field when practice comes to a certain height, and the energy can have shock on the body of oneself. At such circumstances, the Qi field is as a matter of fact an energy field, which could be pooled in the inside and could also be emanated to the outside. The emanated Qi is then what we call “curing by breathing exercise.” Such belongs to the scope of treatment conducted by Taoist doctors.

The transmission of energy in the human hologram reflex does exist in the human hologram field. However, the physical verification of hologram field has to be gradually completed by the mankind. No

matter how this will be described in the future, the final assembly of the field effects could be reduced to the holistic effect of hologram field.

Section IV

Does the Supernatural Power (Super Energy) Exist?

As we discussed in the foregoing, a hologram field is composed of an information field and an energy field. Being an academic term, hologram has often been interpreted as exercise on mental power, or supernatural power, Qi field, mental power field, and some people name it as the field of intention and thoughts. There are many people trying to probe into the field of intention and thoughts, in their mind what people seek after and what people is fear of are intentions and thoughts, which all have energy and might be all realized. This idea is in align with the mind-set that one can be wealthy only if he tries to seek wealth, one can be in love only when he looks for love, one can be in power only if he tries to seek power and one may meet a ghost if he is afraid of ghost. In the end of the Cultural Revolution in China, all the Chinese people were scolding the “Gang of Four”, and then the “Gang of Four” fell. This is exactly what the proverb says, “he who is pointed at by one thousand accusing fingers will die without being ill.”

The Qi field talked about by the Europeans and Americans actually refers to the shocking force of marketing. The Qi field talked about by the Chinese mainly refers to the energy field, to the treatment by the Qi field. Of course, there is probability involved, and probability is the aggregation of the information field.

The great scientist and academician Mr. Qian Xuesen paid special attention to the study of human supernatural power since the 80s in the 20th century. He wrote such words to the Ministry of Publicity of the Party Central Committee: “I pledge with party spirit that human supernatural power is real, not false.” He foretold that life science might be a greater revolution than the 20th century quantum mechanics and the theory of relativity” [3].

Human supernatural power is an objective existence. Professor Li Sicen of electrical machinery, former President of the University of Taiwan discovered after a long period of research on human life that supernatural power can be acquired by the human being during certain age periods after being properly trained and developed.

It should not be questioned that there is discrepancy and exceptions in human heredity and evolution. The physiological ability of ancient people was stronger than modern people, because they faced with a much worse living condition. Among modern people, some have stronger vision, hearing and mental ability than ordinary people. Such people can do things, by applying their special abilities that ordinary people cannot conceive. Such abilities may seem miraculous when people exaggerated them in their talking.

We cannot fully explain the supernatural power with the present scientific means. Because of this fact, the preachers of scientism who believe that only natural science is science, those science fundamentalists who have been alienated by scientism are angry with the study of human supernatural power. Based on their belief that supernatural power is feudal superstition, anti-science and agitating the mainstream ideology, they formed alliance with news media to suppress and hunt down what they thought was “heterodoxy”. By doing so, they successfully strangled some low and purely cheating feudal

superstitions, yet at the same time, they also put a shackle on the projects that were most likely to win a Nobel Prize, such as the project of bio-hologram.

Treatment by way of breathing exercise is scientific, for it is the fitting of the hologram of the bio-magnetic wave with the exterior; it is the development and application of human supernatural power. During the process, the physicians drive away negative energy and information with positive energy and information. The way of munuduction and acupuncture may seem the same between a physician with breathing exercise ability and one without, but the effect is totally different. The physician may decline a request of an entire body munuduction when the Qi field does not fit. For otherwise, the physician himself may be infected with ill Qi while the disease is not dealt with at all. You should be aware that there are some physicians who know how to drive away toxin and supply in time enough Qi to make up his energy and protect himself.

Section V

A Summary—the Hologram Medicine to Be Developed

The hologram medicine is an audacious attempt by both Chinese and foreigners who have a background of medical studies to grafting the hologram in the field of physics to medicine. It is still a discipline to be developed in spite of the fact that it has been often pushed to the side. It is at the same time a new science with bright prospects. It has been just started and still has a long way to go.

The initial application of hologram medicine was based on the research methods of classic Western Medicine. Some Chinese and foreigners with a Western Medicine background inherited and further developed some pure academic hypothesis put forward by Professor Zhang Yingqing in his bio-hologram theory, such as holographic law, holographic element and holographic embryo, and they proposed some new hypotheses on the relative relations between a reflex zone and organs of man, such as eye, ear, hand and foot. Thus, a foundation was laid for a new application theory in the medicine circle, and it is the hologram medicine.

Ever since the idea of reflex zone appeared, the hologram medicine has caught the attention of doctors in the Chinese Medicine, because the reflex zones chosen by hologram medicine are almost identical to the exterior images of organs inside a human body described by the Chinese Medicine, such an agreement was reached without any prior exchange of views between the two sides. There is a shadow of Chinese Medicine in hologram medicine, for the reflex zones are almost organ graphics in the Chinese Medicine. Yet, in the hologram medicine there isn't the concept of Qi in it.

The hologram medicine made a formal come-back to China at the end of the last century. In 1996, Jiao Chunrong, Tian Daozheng and others published "A Complete Collection of Papers on the Hologram Medicine", which is a summary of the nation's first symposium on hologram medicine held in Yantai city of Shandong Province in August, 1994. In 2009, experts of the Chinese Medicine Mr. Li Xingguang, Guo Changqing and others wrote a book "Hologram in the Chinese Medicine", which added the content of the Chinese Medicine into hologram medicine.

The above-mentioned experts and other scholars of the Chinese Medicine made their precious contribution to popularization of hologram in the Chinese Medicine at their respective levels by combining meridian, acupuncture points and the four examinations in the Chinese Medicine with hologram medicine.

Hologram is simply a short form of the entire information; therefore, it is a holistic theory, and has a natural kinship with the Chinese Medicine. Having stated the above, we wish to point out that the purpose of putting forward in this book the idea of human holographic reflex on basis of what our precedents have done is to enrich the content of hologram medicine, and to provide more food for thought for our posterity who are expected to perfect this discipline.

The Western Medicine does not recognize the fact that there is Qi inside a human body, and naturally, its doctors would not cure diseases by adjusting Qi. What the Western Medicine relies on are drugs and surgical operations in treating diseases. So, what the hologram reflex describes is not attractive at all to the doctors of the Western Medicine, and the Western Medicine does not have the fortune to be related with hologram reflex. Meanwhile, the Chinese Medicine, which relies on Qi and the meridian to cure the patients, is closely related to the standpoint, views and methods of hologram. We are deeply convinced that once human holographic reflex becomes a full-fledged discipline and enters into class rooms, it would broaden the vision of the Chinese Medicine and shine aurora on the future development of the Chinese Medicine.

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